

TOURISM TERMINOLOGY AND ITS CLASSIFICATIONS

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***Annotation:** This article is devoted to investigating semantic and structural peculiarities of tourism terminology. In the article, the study made it possible to identify typological features of the terminology of the tourism sector in Uzbek, and English, that is, to establish similarities and differences in the structure, semantics, sources of appearance and history of the formation and development of terms. The terminology system of the tourism sector is an internally organized collection of interconnected and interconnected units that have been formed for several centuries.*

***Keywords:** terminology, tourism, research, lexico-semantic, structural, terminology system, interrelated and interconnected units, tourism terminology.*

INTRODUCTION

General linguistics is divided into several groups, for instance lexicology, etymology, phraseology, terminology and so on. The terminology of any branch of knowledge is always in a state of quantitative and qualitative change: some terms are outdated and out of use, others arise and are introduced; changes the semantic scope of previously known terms; the values are redistributed. This suggests the activity of lexico semantic relations in terminology, which proceed somewhat differently from the literary language [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The work "General Terminology" indicates the peculiarities of the phenomena of polysemy, homonymy and synonymy: "If in general vocabulary such phenomena as polysemy, homonymy, synonymy is consistently presented, then in special vocabulary they have their own characteristics and limitations. Thus, as desired

requirements for terms, unambiguity is distinguished, that is, one word - one meaning, which means that the term does not have polysemantic relations, homonyms, synonyms. In practice, this is not the case [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A study of tourism terms showed that synonymy is observed more often in the terminology system of the Uzbek, Russian language than English. So, in the studied corps, synonyms are 33% among Uzbek, 12% among Russians and 18.5% among English terms of tourism. Researchers call the main reasons for the emergence of synonyms in terminology: 1) parallel termination of the concept by several researchers; 2) various translations of the term; 3) the presence of a complete and short designation of one concept; 4) coexistence of eponymous and ordinary terms [3,21]. Tourism terminology is most characterized by synonymy, which appears for the first three reasons.

Based on these concepts, we classified English and Russian synonyms of tourism terminology and obtained the following data. An analysis of the sample of English terms in the tourism sector showed that 98 terms (9.9% of the total sample) have options in this language. In the Russian sample, this number is 118 (16.9%). Taking into account the level of the language system, the following types of options are noted.

1) Graphic - terms that differ only in spelling. English synonyms of this kind are presented in the amount of 18 units, which is 18.4% of the number of all sample options. Example: traveler - traveller, pressurization — pressurisation, familiarization trip — familiarization trip, travel catalog — travel catalogue, traveler's check — traveller's cheque, appetizer — appetiser, camping site - campingsite. In English tourism terminology, the presence of graphic variants is primarily due to differences between the British and American versions of the language [4].

2) Phonetic variants are variants that differ only in pronunciation. Synonyms of this kind are presented only in English in the number of 12 units, which

is 12.2% of the number of all sampling options: scheduled/light f'jedju: ldj - ['skedju: ld], valet parking f'vcelij - f'vceleij, transit f'trcensitj - [' tramzit], boarding pass [p'peleij In most cases, variants of different pronunciation of terms arise due to differences between the British and American versions of the language, which leads to an increase in the number of phonetic variants in the English terminology of the tourism sector.

3) Phonetic-graphic variants - variants that differ only in pronunciation and variant spelling of identical lexes. In English us 8 similar options (8.2%) were revealed: snorkeling ['snoiklirj] - snorkelling ['sno: kdlin], agrotourism ['cegrdvotvdri:m] - agritourism ['cegriotvdri:m], barber's shop [Ja: b̩ɜr fop] - barber shop [Ja: b̩ɜ J op], draft [dra: ft] - draft [draft].

4) Word-forming variants - variants that differ in derivational affixes or the order of the elements. In the English sample, this type of variant is less significantly represented - only 8 terms (8.2%): shopping tour - shop tour, yachting tourism - yachttourism, camping site - campsite, turning down - turndown. Uzbek word-formation options are presented in the amount of 12 units (10.2%): club-hotel - hotel-club, snowboarding - snowboarding, flight - flight, caravan - car caravan, non-stop flight - non-stop flight, traveler - traveling.

5) Syntactic variants - variants-phrases that differ in the syntactic model of formation (word order and relations between them). Synonyms of this kind are presented in the amount of 10 units in English (10.2%), Uzbek (7.1%): date of departure - departure date, date of arrival - arrival date, country of origin - origin country, tourism demand - demand for tourism, tourism infrastructure - infrastructure of tourism, guest house - guest house, hotel catalogue - hotel.

6) Morphological-syntactic variants are variants, one of which is a term-phrase or a complex term, and the other is its short variant obtained by syntactic or morphological transformations. The following varieties of morphological syntactic variants are distinguished: - elliptical, formed by passing one of the elements of the

multicomponent term without changing its meaning. In English, 16 such terms were noted (16.3%): farm stay tourism - farm tourism, healthcare tourism - health tourism, ground handling operator - ground operator, day tripper - tripper, world round tour - world tour, scuba diving - diving, commission - commission, tourist product information - tourist information, tour with educational goals - educational tour, block charter - block, baggage allowance - baggage allowance, tourist class bus - tourist bus; - composite, formed by adding words or basics of a multi-component term.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, an analysis of the actual material showed that in the terminology of the tourism sector of the Uzbek and English languages the terms-antonyms of the contradictor, complementary and counter type prevail. So, the analysis of semantic and structural relations gives us the opportunity to conclude that the main semantic relations are characteristic of tourist terminology of both Uzbek, and English. At the same time, significant differences were found in the buildings of the languages studied regarding the activity of semantic and structural relations, which testify to the more mature state of the Uzbek, English terminology of the tourism sector.

REFERENCES

1. Beaver A. A Dictionary of Travel and Tourism Terminology. Second edition. Oxon: CABI Publishing, 2005. - 395 p
2. Danilenko V.P. Russian terminology: experience of linguistic description. -M.: Science, 1977.-246 p.
3. Dictionary of Leisure, Travel and Tourism. Third edition. London: A&C Black Publishers Ltd, 2006. - 378 p.
4. Gassling S., Hall CM., Weaver D.B. Sustainable tourism futures. UK: Taylor&Francis, 2008. - 288 p
5. Golovin B.N. Terminology//Berezin F.M., Golovin B.N. General

linguistics. -M.:Enlightenment, 1979. - P. 264 - 278.